

PRINCIPALS' LEADERSHIP STYLES ON TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN UYO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the influence of principals' leadership styles on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Two specific objectives were formulated to determine the influence of autocratic and democratic leadership styles on teachers' job satisfaction. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a survey research design. The population comprised 925 teachers in 15 public secondary schools, while a sample of 250 teachers was selected using simple random sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled *Principals' Leadership Styles and Teachers' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (PLSTJSQ)*, designed on a four-point Likert scale. Data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions, while dependent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that autocratic leadership style had a significant influence on teachers' job satisfaction, though negatively inclined, while democratic leadership style had a high positive and significant influence on teachers' job satisfaction. Based on the findings, it was concluded that democratic leadership style is more effective in enhancing teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools. It was recommended, among others, that principals should adopt participatory leadership practices and that educational authorities should provide continuous leadership training for school administrators.

Keywords: *Leadership style, autocratic leadership, democratic leadership, teachers' job satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is the ability to influence and guide individuals or groups toward the achievement of set goals. It is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common objective. As a leader, the principals are involved in developing the school vision, bringing innovation in teachers' teaching methods, promoting staff performance, organizing instructional activities and promoting effective school climate. These roles are indispensable to better worker performance. Furthermore, it is the responsibility of the principals to provide instructional leadership which entails ensuring high quality teaching and learning by supervising instructional programme and ensuring effective use of instructional time to foster the attainment of educational goals and objectives. Onuma (2016) asserted that the principal has the primary functions of exhibiting effective leadership practices for the improvement of diversified curriculum and quality of instructional programme for effective attainment of set school goals. Achimugu and Obaka (2019) averred that the school principal is the administrator and chief executive of the institution, community and public relation facilitator, curriculum and instructional supervisor or budget facilitator, a change agent, an evaluator, a counselor, conflict reconciler, students' personal organizer, and a leader, among others. Therefore, the principal plays a significant role in the school.

Leadership style is generally use to mean the administrative and leadership behaviour and attitude exhibited by the principal in the administration of the school under his care. To effectively administer the school, Achimugu and Obaka (2019) noted that there must be leadership characteristics that a principal must exhibit to direct the activities of the staff and students toward the achievement of the school goals. These leadership characteristics of principals are sometimes referred to as leadership styles. Leadership style is categorized into autocratic, democratic, laissez faire and uninvolved. These styles are based on the different levels of demand and control tendency of the principal. Principal's autocratic leadership style focuses on dominating attitude that does not recognize opposing or

competing views. According to Achimugu and Obaka (2019) autocratic principals provide no opportunities for alternative views or interest other than those defined by himself as the legitimate leader. Autocratic leadership style also known as authoritarian leadership style typically does not support delegation of responsibilities and are always alienated from their subordinates. This type of leadership often engenders anger, frustration, despair, and in extreme cases withdrawal from school activities. From behaviour wise, Cherry (2013) argued that authoritarian principals attempt to shape, control and evaluate the behaviour of teachers and students without considering their feelings. Teachers are required to follow rules without any explanations from the principal. According to Njami and Bula (2018) autocratic principal leadership instills fear to staff and therefore the followers accomplish the tasks assigned to because of fear of disciplinary action.

Njami and Bula (2018) further asserted that an autocratic leadership style may achieve a high degree of compliance and order among school workers but does not foster trust or collaborative relationships between the principal and staff. Job satisfaction refers to the degree to which teachers are content with the job that they perform. It is conceptualized as a dynamic structure determined by the interaction among many factors. It is the teacher's overall emotional experience and cognitive expression of their occupation, working conditions and state (Phillips and Connell, 2023). Job satisfaction encompasses a positive emotional response to teaching responsibilities, working conditions, interpersonal relationships, and the level of recognition and reward received for their efforts. It is an essential component of teacher motivation, commitment, and overall professional effectiveness. According to Oboegbulem and Onwurah (2021), job satisfaction among teachers is the degree to which they perceive their work as rewarding and aligned with their personal and professional goals, which in turn influences their attitude, performance, and retention. Job satisfaction is shaped by several factors including the school environment, leadership style of administrators, opportunities for professional development, and relationships with students and

colleagues. Teachers who perceive their work environment as supportive and respectful are more likely to experience satisfaction and engage positively in the teaching-learning process. Akomolafe and Adesua (2022) observed that supportive administrative practices, clear communication, and participatory decision-making contribute significantly to teachers' sense of satisfaction and morale. When these elements are absent, dissatisfaction can set in, leading to a decline in productivity and enthusiasm. It has been observed in most schools that teachers' job satisfaction has resulted in poor attitude to work among teachers. Some teachers still come to school late, some are irregular in class, some leave school before closing time, some do not partake in school activities like morning devotion, staff meeting among others.

A major issue influencing teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools relates to prevailing working conditions and the level of motivation available to staff. Many school workers operate in environments characterized by inadequate infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, insufficient instructional materials, and limited access to modern facilities and equipment which constrain effective task execution (Okeke and Eze, 2021). Such unfavourable conditions often lower morale and reduce productivity. In addition, irregular payment of salaries, lack of fringe benefits, minimal opportunities for promotion, and weak incentive structures have been identified as factors that weaken workers' commitment to duty (Akinwale, 2020). Furthermore, leadership practices and the organizational climate within secondary schools further shape teachers' job satisfaction and institutional outcomes. This implies that the leadership style adopted by principals could determine the level of staff morale, job satisfaction and willingness to perform assigned duties effectively. Uche and Nwankwo (2020) examined the influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Onitsha North Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that autocratic leadership style had a significant negative influence on teachers' job performance, particularly in instructional delivery and commitment to

duty. Okafor and Eze (2019) examined the relationship between principals' leadership styles and teachers' work performance in public secondary schools in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State, Nigeria. The topic of the study was Principals' Leadership Styles and Teachers' Work Performance in Public Secondary Schools. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design and was guided by five research questions and five hypotheses. The population consisted of all principals and teachers in the zone, while a sample of 300 teachers was selected using proportionate random sampling technique. Results revealed that autocratic leadership style significantly reduced teachers' motivation and work performance.

Ezeh and Nwoye (2020) investigated leadership styles as correlates of workers' commitment in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational research design and was guided by four research questions and four hypotheses. The population consisted of all teachers in the area, while a sample of 210 teachers was selected using systematic sampling technique. Results revealed that autocratic leadership style had a significant negative relationship with workers' commitment and performance. Edet and Umoh (2021) investigated the effect of democratic leadership style on staff productivity in public secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study employed a correlational research design guided by four research questions and four hypotheses. The population consisted of 350 teaching and non-teaching staff, with a sample of 210 respondents drawn using stratified random sampling. Results indicated that democratic leadership style significantly enhanced staff productivity through participatory decision-making and collaborative problem-solving. Okereke and Onuoha (2022) investigated the influence of democratic leadership style on employees' commitment and performance in public secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. The population included all teachers in the selected

schools, with a sample of 180 drawn using simple random sampling. Findings indicated that democratic leadership style positively influenced employees' commitment and performance by fostering participatory governance and effective communication.

Ekanem and Udoh (2021) examined the effect of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction and productivity in public secondary schools in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey research design guided by four research questions and four hypotheses. Results revealed that democratic leadership style significantly enhanced teachers' job satisfaction and productivity. Although, studies on principal's leadership style has replete, most of these studies concentrate on its correlation with academic performance, behavioural problems in secondary school. Studies on principal's leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area are scanty thereby creating gap in knowledge and understanding. Therefore, this study sought to determine the relationship between principals' leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Teachers' job satisfaction is expected to enhance effectiveness teaching and learning in secondary schools as it directly influences teachers' motivation, commitment, instructional delivery and overall school performance. In an ideal school system, teachers are expected to demonstrate high levels of enthusiasm, dedication, and professional engagement. However, observations revealed that in many secondary schools, particularly within Uyo Local Government Area, a significant number of teachers' exhibit signs of dissatisfaction with their jobs. This dissatisfaction is often reflected in behaviours such as absenteeism, low commitment to instructional duties, poor interpersonal relationships, reduced productivity, and in some cases, intention to leave the profession. One of the major concerns in secondary schools is that teachers' job satisfaction appears to be

significantly influenced by the leadership styles adopted by school principals. In many schools, principals, who are expected to create supportive and motivating work environments, seem to adopt leadership approaches that do not adequately address teachers' professional and emotional needs. These practices provide little guidance and supervision that could create unfavourable working conditions. Such leadership practices can lead to low morale, feelings of neglect, lack of recognition, and reduced sense of belonging among teachers. Consequently, teachers may become frustrated, disengaged, and less committed to their duties. This situation raises serious concerns about the extent to which principals' leadership styles contribute to the persistent issue of low job satisfaction among teachers in secondary schools. Furthermore, there is limited empirical evidence specifically addressing how principals' leadership styles influence teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools within Uyo Local Government Area. This gap makes it difficult for educational stakeholders to design appropriate interventions aimed at improving teachers' working conditions and enhancing school effectiveness. It is against this background that this study seeks to investigate the relationship between principals' leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the influence of principals' leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area. Specifically, the study examined:

- i) The influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area
- ii) the influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area

Research Questions

Two research questions guided the study

- i) What is the influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area?
- ii) What is the influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area?

Research Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were formulated and test at .05 level of significance.

- i) There is no significance influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area
- ii) There is no significance influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area

Research Design

A Survey research design was adopted for the study. Survey research design is a method of collecting data from a population of interest in order to describe existing conditions, opinions, behaviours, or relationships among variables without manipulating them. This design was considered suitable for the study because it enabled the researcher to investigate the influence of leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools without manipulating any of the variables.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised 925 teachers in the 15 public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area during the 2025/2026 academic session (Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board, 2026).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 250 teachers was selected for the study. The sample size represented 27.02 percent of the entire population. A simple random sampling technique was adopted to select 10 public secondary schools from the area. In each school, a balloting method was used to

select 25 teachers. This procedure ensured that all students had equal opportunity of being selected for the study.

Instrumentation

A structured questionnaire known as Principal Leadership Styles and Teacher' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (PLSTJSQ) was developed and used for data collection. The questionnaire items were structured on a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), weighted 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

Method of Data Analysis

Mean, standard deviation, and p value derived from dependent t test analysis were used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses at .05 alpha level.

Research Question One:

What is the influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area?

Table 1: Summary of dependent t test analysis of the influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools

Variables	n	Mean	Std	Correlation coefficient	P-value
Autocratic leadership style	250	14.26	2.98	.438	.002
Teachers' job satisfaction	250	61.35	7.82		

The result in Table 1 shows the influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools. The result shows that the mean responses of teachers on autocratic leadership style and job satisfaction are 14.26 and 61.35 respectively, which leads to a mean difference of 47.09. The standard deviations also show that the teachers did not differ much in their responses on autocratic leadership style and job satisfaction. The moderate mean difference

produces a correlation coefficient of .438 that is significant because $p = .002$ to show that autocratic leadership style has a significant influence on teachers' job satisfaction. Hence, this result indicates that autocratic leadership style influences teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Research Question Two:

What is the influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area?

Table 2: Summary of dependent t test analysis of the influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools

Variables	n	Mean	Std	Correlation coefficient	P-value
Democratic leadership style	250	17.88	3.15	.562	.000
Teachers' job satisfaction	250	61.35	7.82		

The result in Table 2 shows the influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools. The result shows that the mean responses of teachers on democratic leadership style and job satisfaction are 17.88 and 61.35 respectively, which leads to a mean difference of 43.47. The standard deviations also show that the teachers did not differ much in their responses on democratic leadership style and job satisfaction. The high mean difference produces a correlation coefficient of .562 that is significant because $p = .000$ to show that democratic leadership style has high influence on teachers' job satisfaction. Hence, this result indicates that democratic leadership style greatly influences teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Hypothesis One:

There is no significant influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Table 3: Summary of dependent t test analysis of the influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision at $P \leq .05$ alpha
Autocratic leadership style	250	14.26	2.98	54.62	.002	Significant
Teachers' job satisfaction	250	61.35	7.82			

significant at $p \leq .05$, $df = 249$

The result in Table 3 shows whether there is significant influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools. The result indicates that the t-value of 54.62 is significant because the p-value of .002 is less than .05 alpha level. Hence, there is a significant influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Table 4: Summary of dependent t test analysis of the influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools

Variables	n	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision at $P \leq .05$ alpha
Democratic leadership style	250	17.88	3.15	72.34	.000	Significant
Teachers' job satisfaction	250	61.35	7.82			

significant at $p \leq .05$, $df = 249$

The result in Table 4 shows whether there is significant influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools. The result indicates that the t-value of 72.34 is significant because the p-value of .000 is less than .05 alpha level. Hence, there is a significant influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study revealed that autocratic leadership style has a significant influence on teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area. The result showed a moderate correlation coefficient ($r = .438$, $p < .05$), indicating that the leadership approach adopted by principals plays a crucial role in shaping how teachers perceive their work environment. However, given the nature of autocratic leadership, which is characterised by strict control, limited teacher participation in decision-making, and top-down communication, the implication is that such influence is largely negative on job satisfaction. This finding aligns with the earlier study by Uche and Nwankwo (2020), which reported that autocratic leadership style significantly reduced teachers' job performance and commitment to duty. Similarly, Okafor and Eze (2019) found that autocratic leadership negatively affected teachers' motivation and overall work performance.

The study further revealed that democratic leadership style has a high and significant influence on teachers' job satisfaction ($r = .562$, $p <$

.05), indicating a stronger relationship compared to autocratic leadership style. This finding suggests that when principals adopt participatory and inclusive leadership approaches, teachers are more likely to experience higher levels of satisfaction in their jobs. Democratic leadership is characterised by shared decision-making, open communication, mutual respect, and recognition of teachers' contributions, all of which foster a supportive and motivating work environment. This result is in agreement with the findings of Edet and Umoh (2021), who reported that democratic leadership significantly enhanced staff productivity through collaborative problem-solving and participatory governance. Likewise, Okereke and Onuoha (2022) found that democratic leadership positively influenced employees' commitment and performance, while Ekanem and Udoh (2021) established that it improved teachers' job satisfaction and productivity. The convergence of these studies with the present findings underscores the importance of leadership style in educational administration.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that principals' leadership styles play a significant role in determining teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area. The study established that autocratic leadership style has a significant influence on teachers' job satisfaction, though its effect is largely unfavourable due to its rigid, controlling, and non-participatory nature. Teachers working under such leadership tend to experience low morale, limited motivation, and reduced sense of belonging, which negatively affects their overall job satisfaction. On the other hand, democratic leadership style was found to have a stronger and more positive influence on teachers' job satisfaction. This is because democratic leadership promotes inclusiveness, open communication, mutual respect, and shared decision-making, all of which contribute to a supportive and motivating work environment. The findings therefore underscore the importance of leadership approach in enhancing teachers' psychological well-being,

commitment, and effectiveness in the school system. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

- i) Principals should adopt democratic and participatory leadership practices by involving teachers in decision-making, maintaining open communication to reduce morale and job satisfaction.
- ii) The Ministry of Education should provide continuous leadership training and enforce supportive leadership policies in order to improve teachers' job satisfaction and overall school performance.

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